

Synthesis and Reactions of 2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-Aryl-1:3-Butadienes

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Condensation of diethyl-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconate (I) with various aromatic aldehydes furnished a series of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acids (II), which upon thermal decarboxylation formed corresponding 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1:3-butadienes (III). Application of Diels-Alder reaction to (III) gave 3-aryl-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1:2:3:6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydrides (IV), while bromination of (III) yielded dibromides of the type (V).

The synthesis of unsymmetrically aryl butadienes like 1:2:4-triphenyl-1:3-butadiene and 2:3-diaryl-1:3-butadiene has been done in several ways¹⁻⁴, including the thermal decarboxylation of corresponding acids.⁵⁻⁸ We have achieved the synthesis of 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1:3-butadienes (III) through the thermal decarboxylation of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acids (II).

Claisen Aldol condensation between diethyl-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconate⁹ and various aromatic aldehydes in the presence of excess of sodium ethoxide¹⁰ furnished after saponification of the product 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acids (II), (Table 1), as confirmed through their neutral equivalent and elemental analysis.

Thermal decarboxylation of (II) yielded corresponding 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadienes (III), (Table 2). UV of (III, R = H) revealed absorption peaks at λ_{max} 208 and λ_{max} 259 m μ (ϵ_{max} 24190 and 14140 respectively).^{11,12}

Diels-Alder reaction with 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadienes (III): An optimum yield of 3-aryl-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1 : 2 : 3 : 6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydrides (IV) was obtained by treating equimolar quantities of (III) and maleic anhydride in xylene at reflux for 10 hrs.¹³ However, modifications of experimental conditions¹⁴ increased the yield of (IV) considerably. Formation of (IV) (Table 3) was confirmed through elemental analysis, IR spectral studies and their ability to form a fluorescein dye. IR of (IV) exhibited a strong band at 1710 cm^{-1} and a weak, at 1880 cm^{-1} (carbonyl groups of cyclic anhydride which have a strong lower frequency),¹⁵ a peak at 1640 cm^{-1} (cyclohexene ring)¹⁶ and bands at 1210 cm^{-1} and 1260 cm^{-1} (C-O-C stretching vibrations)¹⁷ thus lending conclusive support to the structure assigned.

Bromination of 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadienes (III): Bromination of (III) was carried out under the condition similar to those described by Huggins and Yokley.¹⁸ The elemental analysis (carbon, hydrogen and halogen) accounted for the formation of a dibromide rather than a tetrabromide. That, in the dibromide, the double bond remains intact was supported by positive Beyer's test¹⁹ and IR spectral studies.

Three dibromides are theoretically possible, depending upon whether 1 : 4, 1 : 2 or 3 : 4 addition has taken place. Exhaustive oxidation of the dibromide (R = H) using permanganate in acetone solution afforded an acid and an aldehyde, the presence of latter being confirmed by the customary Schiff's reagent test. The formation of an aldehyde eliminates a 3 : 4-addition, as, such an addition would not give an aldehyde on oxidation

under identical conditions. IR of the dibromide (R = H) revealed a peak at 810 cm^{-1} (out of plane = CH vibrations of trisubstituted ethylenes of the type V, $\left(\begin{array}{c} R_1-C-R_2 \\ || \\ R_3-C-H \end{array} \right)^{20}$). The products, therefore, appear to be 1 : 4-addition products (V), (Table 4).

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected. UV spectra were measured in methanol on Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer. IR (nujol) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord 237 or Hilger-Watts Infracan H 900.

3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acid (II), (Table 1) : A mixture of diethyl-3-(4'-methoxyphenyl) glutaconate (I) (2.92 g., 0.01 mole) and freshly distilled aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mole) was dissolved in about 15 ml of absolute ethanol. To this mixture was added dropwise a solution of sodium (0.8 g.) in absolute ethanol (10 ml), when a white solid separated. After keeping overnight the solid was heated with excess of 1N KOH on a steam bath (1 hr.). The alkaline extract was cooled, filtered and washed with ether. Acidification of alkaline extract with conc. HCl afforded crude (II) which was crystallized either from glacial acetic acid or absolute ethanol.

TABLE 1

Analytical data of 3-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acids (II)

Sr. No.	R	m.p. °C	S	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis, %			
						Required C	Required H	Found C	Found H
1	H	228-29	a	87	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₆	70.37	4.97	70.27	5.11
2	4-OCH ₃	205-07	a	88	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₆	67.79	5.12	67.52	5.40
3	4-Cl	238-40	b	84	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ Cl	63.59	4.21	63.32	4.11
4	3-NO ₂	215-16	b	90	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₇ N	61.79	4.10	61.44	4.28
5	4-N $\begin{cases} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{cases}$	223-25	c	90	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N	68.63	5.76	68.33	5.42

S = Solvent for crystallization : a—glacial acetic acid, b—absolute ethanol, c—50% ethanol.

2-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadiene (III) (Table 2) : 3-(4'-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(substituted benzylidene) glutaconic acid (II) (10 g.) was taken in a dry Erlenmeyer flask and heated to the melting point on a paraffin bath. The acid melted with a brisk evolution of CO₂ and heating was continued till all CO₂ evolved. Upon cooling a dark brown semi-viscous mass was obtained. This mass was treated with saturated aqueous bicarbonate (100 ml) to ensure removal of unchanged acid. Repeated crystallization from appropriate solvent using activated charcoal gave pure (III).

TABLE 2

Analytical data of 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadienes (III)

Sr. No.	R	m.p. °C	S	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis, %			
						Required C	Required H	Found C	Found H
1	H	85-86	a	86	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O	86.40	6.83	86.28	6.97
2	4-OCH ₃	108-10	a	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ O ₂	81.19	6.81	81.49	6.60
3	4-Cl	112-14	b	95	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ OCl	75.39	5.58	75.29	5.72
4	3-NO ₂	98-99	a	91	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	72.57	5.38	72.89	5.16
5	4- $\begin{cases} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{cases}$	170-72	c	84	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ ON	81.63	7.58	81.52	7.49

Solvent for crystallization : a—absolute ethanol, b—50% ethanol, c—50% acetic acid.

3-Aryl-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-1 : 2 : 3 : 6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydride (IV), (Table 3) : *Method A* : A mixture of 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadiene (III) (0.01 mole) and maleic anhydride (0.98 g., 0.01 mole) in xylene (60 ml.) was refluxed for 10 hrs. Upon cooling and standing the adduct deposited as shining crystals which were filtered and washed well with water to remove traces of maleic anhydride, leaving pure (IV).

TABLE 3

Analytical data of 3-aryl-5-(4'-methoxyphenyl)1,2,3,6-tetrahydrophthalic anhydrides (IV)

Sr. No.	R	m.p. °C	S	Yield* %	Molecular formula	Analysis, %				
						Required		Found		
					C	H	C	H		
1	H	133-35	a	51	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₄	75.45	5.43	74.96	4.89	
2	4-OCH ₃	127-28	a	44	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	72.49	5.53	72.17	5.81	
3	4-Cl	195-97	b	54	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ ClO ₄	68.37	4.65	68.25	4.23	
4	3-NO ₂	185-86	c	48	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₆	66.46	4.52	66.08	4.18	
5	4-N < CH ₃ CH ₃	214-16	b	35	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ NO ₄	73.18	6.14	72.83	6.29	

* Figures represent the yields obtained by using method B.

S = Solvent for crystallization : a—50% ethanol; b—absolute ethanol; c—glacial acetic acid.

Method B : Maleic anhydride (0.98 g., 0.01 mole) was melted on a sand bath with 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadiene (III) (0.01 mole) and heated for 3 hrs. to the melting temperature. The melt was mixed with water and filtered. The crude product was crystallized from appropriate solvent giving pure (IV).

1-Bromo-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-4-bromo-2-butene (V), (Table 4) : 2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-1 : 3-butadiene (III) (0.01 mole) was dissolved in freshly distilled chloroform and cooled to 0° in ice-salt bath. To this solution was added dropwise with constant stirring a solution of bromine (2.6 g.) in chloroform (20 ml.). After allowing it to stand overnight, the solvent was removed under *vacuo* at room temperature. The solid thus obtained was crystallized from appropriate solvent using norit.

TABLE 4

Analytical data of 1-bromo-2-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4-aryl-4-bromo-2-butenes (V)

Sr. No.	R	m.p. °C	S	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis, %					
						Required			Found		
					C	H	Br	C	H	Br	
1	H	190-92	a	63	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ Br ₂ O	51.54	4.07	40.34	51.36	3.98	40.31
2	4-OCH ₃	168-70	a	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ Br ₂ O ₂	50.74	4.26	37.50	50.62	4.19	37.10
3	4-Cl	154-55	b	77	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ ClBr ₂ O	47.42	3.51	45.35*	47.13	3.09	44.97*
4	3-NO ₂	174-75	c	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NBr ₂ O ₃	46.29	3.43	36.23	46.32	3.76	35.82

* Total halogen content.

S = Solvent for crystallization ; a—absolute ethanol; b—dioxan; c—methanol,

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